

Youth Goals

Research Centre

JEAN MONNET MODULE

Report

Structured Dialogues

Salamanca University of Salamanca

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1st Structured Dialogue

Alonso Escamilla

01/03/2023

OVERVIEW

The presentation entitled "*The application of statistics in European projects*", given by Alonso Escamilla (Project Coordinator at BB&R), took place within the framework of the VI Contact Cycle. The content focused on the trajectory of BB&R and the relevance of statistics to promote social and international projects, with a special emphasis on programmes aimed at youth.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To present the trajectory and experience of BB&R: from its origins in 2010, through the incubation phase in the Chamber of Commerce of Salamanca, to the consolidation in Gran Vía.
- To highlight the importance of statistics and data analysis in the implementation and evaluation of public and private projects, particularly in the field of youth.
- Show examples of successful projects: both at national and international level, highlighting the cross-cutting nature of the initiatives (training, social innovation, community development, electoral processes, etc.).
- Emphasise the need to measure impact and tailor projects to the needs of target groups, incorporating quantitative evidence for decision-making.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation by the rapporteur: Alonso Escamilla
Conference: " <i>The application of statistics in European projects</i> ".
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the event and speaker.

The presentation, entitled "*The application of statistics in European projects*", was part of the VI Business Contact Cycle held in March 2023. The conference was given by Alonso Escamilla, Project Coordinator at BB&R, who has extensive experience in the implementation of social and international initiatives. In his presentation, Escamilla highlighted the organisation's track record and the value of statistics in designing, evaluating and optimising projects aimed primarily at young people.

Conference: "The application of statistics in European projects".

During the presentation, an overview of the origins of BB&R, founded in 2010 by three students from the University of Salamanca, and its growth into a multidisciplinary team (Political Science, Statistics, International Relations, Psychology, Engineering) was given.

Several projects focused on public policy, social innovation and electoral processes were also presented, always emphasising the relevance of quantitative evidence to identify trends and measure impacts. Examples were mentioned such as job and training opportunities platforms, social theatre activities or digital gaming projects, all of them supported by statistical bases that facilitate decision-making.

Dialogue

After the lecture, a space was opened for questions and reflections from the audience - mostly young students and representatives of youth organisations. Topics addressed included:

- Statistical techniques used in the planning and implementation of social projects.
- How to adapt projects to the real needs of young people.
- The value of data analysis as a tool for making problems visible and proposing viable solutions.

Alonso Escamilla explained the keys to ensuring that projects support the participation of youth groups and meet their expectations, inviting young people to train in digital skills and statistics in order to directly influence management and social innovation.

Conclusions and closure.

In his concluding remarks, Escamilla stressed the importance of collaboration between institutions, private entities and youth themselves to enhance the success of European-wide projects. He invited participants to explore the digital resources and platforms offered by BB&R, and to maintain a data-driven approach to any initiative seeking real impact.

Prior to the closing of the session, a satisfaction survey was carried out among the participants in order to improve those aspects that the participants considered relevant in the following dialogues.

The session concluded by thanking all attendees, highlighting the need to join forces and harness the strength of statistical evidence to design policies and programmes capable of responding effectively to today's youth challenges

2nd Structured Dialogue

Paulo Portas

30/11/2023

OVERVIEW

Paulo Portas, former Minister of Foreign Affairs and Deputy Prime Minister of Portugal, gave a lecture on "*New current challenges for the European Union in the field of youth*" to a university audience and specialists interested in the development of youth policies. The speaker brought his experience in the international arena and his extensive political career to address the need to establish indicators and evaluations that guarantee the effectiveness of the strategies designed for the benefit of European youth.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To present the vision of an expert in international relations and European politics on the challenges facing youth on the continent.
- Emphasise the importance of strong systems for measuring and monitoring employment, education, political participation and social welfare indicators.
- Emphasise the importance of rigorous and evidence-based evaluations for the continuous improvement of interventions targeting young Europeans.
- Raise awareness of the need for timely corrections and adaptation of policies to adequately address the needs of the youth population.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation by the rapporteur: Paulo Portas
Conference: " <i>New challenges facing the European Union today in the field of youth</i> ".
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the event and the speaker.

It began with a brief introduction to the career of Paulo Portas, mentioning his positions as Minister of Foreign Affairs and Deputy Prime Minister of Portugal, as well as his contributions in the field of strategic consultancy and university teaching.

The relevance of their experience in analysing the challenges of the European Union and the importance of measuring and evaluating youth policies was emphasised.

Conference: "New challenges facing the European Union today in the field of youth".

Portas explained the urgency of establishing reliable indicators to properly diagnose the situation of young people in key areas such as employment, education and political participation.

He stressed the need for continuous monitoring mechanisms, so that the policies implemented can be adjusted in an agile and timely manner according to the results obtained.

He underlined the relevance of impact assessments based on empirical evidence, as an indispensable tool to know the real effectiveness of actions and to guide continuous improvement.

Dialogue with participants

After the presentation, the audience actively participated with questions focusing on national and EU challenges, the impact of digitalisation, sustainability and the role of the European Union on the international scene.

Portas responded with concrete examples from his experience in government, illustrating how political decisions can be articulated with citizens' demands to achieve greater consensus.

Strategies for youth participation in politics and the need to integrate the interests of the younger generation into the public agenda were discussed.

Conclusions and closure

The speaker stressed the value of cooperation at EU and international level to share best practices and statistical information.

The importance of actively involving young people in the creation and monitoring of policies that affect them was emphasised, thus promoting greater legitimacy and engagement.

Before the end of the session, a satisfaction survey was carried out among the participants with the aim of identifying and improving those aspects that they considered important for future dialogues.

Finally, participants were invited to reflect on the urgency of investing in youth as an essential pillar for the sustainable development and future competitiveness of the European Union.

3rd Structured Dialogue

Mauricio Bitrán

21/02/2024

OVERVIEW

The structured dialogue "*Crossing science, politics and society in these uncertain times*", given by Mauricio Bitrán, was attended by students and members of the academic community interested in the relevance of scientific evidence for decision-making in public policy. Bitrán, former Deputy Minister of Development of Ontario and professor at the University of Toronto, contributed his experience in the field of international relations and economic development, together with a solid understanding of scientific research and its influence on policy-making.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To explain the importance of using scientific evidence - in particular statistical and epidemiological data - in effective policy making.
- To highlight the different types of scientific studies (in vitro, in vivo, in silico and human studies) and their relevance in assessing the validity of the available evidence.
- Emphasise the need to minimise experimental errors and biases, as well as to appreciate the social determinants that influence the implementation of measures.
- To encourage reflection on the inherent relationship between science, politics and society, and how this synergy determines the effectiveness of public policies.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation of the speaker: Mauricio Bitrán
Conference: " <i>Crossing science, politics and society in these uncertain times</i> ".
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the event and the speaker.

It began with a brief introduction to Mauricio Bitrán's profile, highlighting his experience as a former Ontario Deputy Minister of Development and his role in the negotiation of the Ontario-EU Free Trade Agreement.

The relevance of his academic and professional perspective in addressing the link between scientific evidence and decision-making in times of uncertainty was underlined.

Conference: "Crossing science, politics and society in these uncertain times".

Bitrán described various sources of scientific information (peer-reviewed studies, grey literature, official reports) and explained the need to critically assess their quality.

He outlined the different types of studies (in vitro, in vivo, in silico and human clinical trials) and discussed their advantages and limitations.

He emphasised the relevance of identifying and minimising experimental biases and errors, stressing the importance of rigorous designs.

He stressed that the usefulness of a policy is not only based on the strength of scientific evidence, but also on its degree of acceptability and mainstreaming in society.

Dialogue with participants

Following the presentation, the audience actively participated with questions on how public institutions can incorporate scientific evidence into their planning and evaluation processes.

The importance of clear communication of scientific results, so that citizens understand and support evidence-based initiatives, was addressed.

Some participants shared examples of failed policies due to lack of social consensus, illustrating how the success or failure of a project does not depend solely on its scientific basis.

Conclusions and closure

It was stressed that collaboration between science, politics and society is the basis for developing public policies with a real and lasting impact.

At the end of the session, participants were invited to complete a satisfaction survey to gather their impressions and take them into account in the planning of future dialogues.

The activity concluded with a call to deepen interdisciplinary dialogue, promoting the adoption of scientific evidence and the consideration of the social context as fundamental axes in the formulation of public measures.

4th Structured Dialogue

Susana Malcorra

10/04/2024

OVERVIEW

The structured dialogue "*Analysis of the global situation: a vision from women's leadership*" was given by Susana Malcorra, renowned for her career as Foreign Minister of Argentina, former Chief of Staff of Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon and founder of *GWL Voices*. The event, held in front of a university audience and representatives of civil society, addressed the speed of global change and its implications for geopolitics, democracy and technological disruption, all from the perspective of female leadership and its importance in positions of power.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To provide a comprehensive overview of the main challenges facing the world today, especially in terms of geopolitics, democratic stability and technological transformation.
- To highlight the role of women in global leadership and the need to promote their presence in decision-making positions.
- Introduce *GWL Voices* as an initiative to boost women's participation in positions of power, with the aim of achieving the first UN Secretary General's office to be held by a woman by 2026.
- To invite reflection and debate on the importance of women's leadership networks in the design of solutions to the exponential changes affecting societies.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation by the rapporteur: Susana Malcorra
Conference: " <i>Analysis of the global situation: a view from women's leadership</i> ".
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the event and the speaker.

The session began with an introduction by Susana Malcorra, highlighting her experience at the United Nations and her central role in the creation of *GWL Voices*.

The purpose of the conference and its focus on women's leadership as a key factor in addressing today's global challenges was underlined.

Conference: "Analysis of the global situation: a view from women's leadership".

Malcorra described the exponential transformation that economic, political and social models are undergoing, and explained how the speed of these changes generates instability in different environments. She pointed out three fundamental axes that are affected by these transformations: geopolitics, democracy and technological disruption. She explained the goal of *GWL Voices*: to unite world leaders to promote gender equality in positions of power and, ultimately, to have a woman as UN Secretary General in 2026.

Dialogue and interaction with the public.

Following the presentation, the audience raised questions about women's participation in high politics and the relevance of this leadership for international stability. Concrete examples of how women's collaboration and support networks can influence policy-making and conflict resolution were discussed.

Conclusions and closure.

The importance of inclusive leadership to address new global dynamics and to empower women in decision-making was emphasised.

The relevance of promoting training and debate in the academic sphere as a prior step to influencing major international institutions was highlighted.

A satisfaction survey was given to the participants just before the end of the session, in order to gather their opinions and to continue improving the next meetings according to their contributions.

The event concluded with a call to action for everyone to join initiatives that recognise and empower women's leadership, which is essential to face the challenges of the future.

5th Structured Dialogue

Elena Valenciano

07/11/2024

OVERVIEW

The structured dialogue "*European youth, disillusionment or hope for the future?*" took place at the University of Salamanca, bringing together students and members of civil society interested in learning about and discussing the current situation of youth in Europe. The session was developed around a lecture by Elena Valenciano, a renowned Spanish politician with extensive experience in the European field, followed by an active exchange with the participants.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- To present an up-to-date picture of the reality facing European youth in areas such as mental health, employment, poverty and access to housing.
- To provide a space for reflection on the role of the European Union and the importance of the fight against climate change in improving conditions for young people.
- Emphasise data analysis as an essential tool for the formulation of effective public policies.
- Encourage the direct participation of young people in decision-making processes and in the design of solutions.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation of the speaker: Elena Valenciano
Conference: " <i>European youth: disillusionment or hope for the future?</i> "
Dialogue of the speaker with the participants
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session.

The meeting began with welcoming remarks and a description of the central purpose: to create a space for dialogue on the challenges facing European youth and how institutions and young people themselves can play a role in building a brighter future.

Presentation by the speaker: Elena Valenciano.

A brief outline of her career was given: former member of the European Parliament and the Spanish Parliament, specialising in conflict prevention and dialogue at the Henri Dunant Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue in Geneva. She currently chairs the Women's Foundation, demonstrating her firm commitment to the defence of equality and women's rights.

Conference: "European youth: disillusionment or hope for the future?"

Elena Valenciano presented official data from Eurostat and the European Youth Forum, showing the global and European situation of the youth population in key indicators (employment, mental health, poverty and access to housing).

He underlined the work of the European Union in the fight against climate change as a decisive factor for the future of youth.

He emphasised the need to incorporate data analysis into public policy making and encouraged young people to take an active role in decision-making processes.

Dialogue between the speaker and the participants.

After the lecture, attendees had the opportunity to ask questions and raise reflections. Discussions emerged on labour challenges, inequality of opportunities, the impact of the climate crisis on future generations and the role of education and training in citizen participation.

Conclusions and closure.

The importance of collaboration between institutions, civil society and youth was underlined in order to effectively address the problems identified. Those present were invited to stay informed and to get involved in local and European initiatives that promote the well-being of young people. Thus, the event ended by highlighting the importance of joint action and the use of statistical evidence as a basis for policies that impact on the future of youth. Before the closing of the session, the participants' feedback was collected through a satisfaction survey.

6th Structured Dialogue

Young Voices for the Future

01/04/2025

OVERVIEW

The Final Session of the Youth Goals Research Centre Project marks the end of a participatory and multidisciplinary experience focused on the role of youth in the design and evaluation of public policies. In this meeting, young students from different areas shared reflections and proposals on how to generate fairer, more effective and evidence-based policies. Through open dialogue and collective construction, this session sought to make visible the value of young voices in social transformation.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the event were as follows:

- Visibilise the active role of youth in public decision-making processes.
- Promote the use of data and evidence in the creation and evaluation of youth policies.
- Promote collaboration between young people from different disciplines.
- Develop a collective manifesto with key proposals for the future of youth policies.

AGENDA

The programme of the structured dialogue was as follows:

Presentation of the event and objectives of the session
Presentation of the project and the speakers
Round Table: " <i>Youth and Evidence-Based Policy</i> ".
Dialogue of the speakers with the participants
Creation and reading of the <i>Youth Manifesto for the Future</i>
Conclusions, satisfaction survey and closure

EVENT

1. Welcome and Presentation of the Meeting (Pablo Biderbost)

- Introduction on the key role of young people in the evaluation and design of public policies.
- Brief explanation of the dynamics of the session.

2. Presentation of the project and speakers (Ana Belén Nieto Librero/Nerea González García)

- A brief overview of the main ideas and materials of the Youth Goals Research Centre.
- Presentation of our speakers: the real protagonists of the day, young junior collaborators from different disciplines.

3. Thematic Table: Youth and Evidence-based Policies

How can young people influence public policy? This presentation addressed the role of youth entrepreneurship as a way for young people to actively influence public policy. The speakers argued that fostering startups with social impact, promoting financial education and facilitating access to specialised training can empower young people. They also raised the need to generate alliances between universities, companies and administrations to offer real opportunities for development. They stressed the importance of creating spaces such as entrepreneurship fairs, coworking and collaborative networks, as well as promoting mentoring programmes and access to public incentives. Their intervention underlined that innovation and youth entrepreneurship should be central tools in inclusion and participation strategies (**Samuel David Colina Santana, Alexis Jakel Gómez Crespo and Samuel José Rojas Vielma, Students of the Degree in Political Science - University of Salamanca**).

Why is it important to use data and evidence to design and evaluate policies? This intervention focused on the need to design and evaluate youth policies based on reliable data and empirical evidence. The speakers clearly explained the whole evaluation process: from problem identification to impact measurement, from defining objectives to the implementation of monitoring systems. They underlined the importance of using official indicators, opinion surveys and technologies for real-time monitoring. They also presented initiatives such as Youth Guarantee Plus and Erasmus+ as examples of programmes that require continuous evaluation. They also warned about institutional resistance to the use of data and the existence of analytical biases, calling for the professionalisation of decision-making in youth (**Marta Ruiz de la Hermosa González de la Aleja and Sergio Galán López Students of the Degree in Statistics - University of Salamanca**).

What challenges do we face in implementing effective youth policies and what would you recommend to decision-makers? With a critical and reflective approach, this paper explored the obstacles that youth policies face in order to be truly effective. Through provocative questions such as "Do they really want to listen to us?" or "Are we partly to blame?", the speakers invited to think about representation deficits and the generation gap as structural barriers. They argued for the need to create listening institutions that work in both directions, where youth have a real voice and can generate tangible results. They also pointed out that low youth voter turnout undermines the political influence of young people. Their intervention insisted that the protagonism of youth cannot remain symbolic, but must be materialised in concrete and sustainable decision-making structures (*Ricardo Fernández Maestro and Andrea Machuca Aulisi Students of the Degree in Political Science - University of Salamanca*).

4. Questions and comments from the public.

5. Joint closing: "Youth Manifesto for the Future".

Shared reading and final creation of the manifesto between speakers and attendees. The manifesto is a short statement with the key messages of the project.

The participants complemented the manifesto, using Padlet.

Final satisfaction survey by attendees.

EVALUATION

The evaluation of the six structured dialogues carried out in the framework of the Youth Goals Research Centre project was based on a flexible and adaptive logic, consistent with the participatory and open nature of these activities. Unlike academic courses and conferences, these spaces did not aim at transmitting academic contents, but at fostering horizontal exchange, critical thinking and the expression of university youth around the objectives of European youth policies

Consequently, the application of evaluation instruments varied according to the context of each session. In the first structured dialogue, we opted for a qualitative collection of impressions through open questions on the Studium platform (Moodle), focusing on general feelings, summaries, reflections and highlights of the experience. Although not all the usual items of satisfaction were addressed, the comments collected reflected a positive reception, with emphasis on participation, the approach applied and interest in the topics covered. This experience showed the usefulness of collecting qualitative impressions in participatory contexts, but also highlighted the need to incorporate structured quantitative instruments, such as Likert-type scales, which allow a more precise systematisation of the level of satisfaction with key aspects of the activity. The absence of numerical measurement made comparison with other dialogues difficult and limited the possibility of establishing common indicators of success. This reflection was key to the subsequent design of the questionnaires, especially in the case of the sixth dialogue, where both quantitative scales and open questions were incorporated to offer a more complete and balanced evaluation.

In the second, third and fourth dialogues, structured dialogue activities were organised as a complement to the training programmes in which they were framed, with the aim of enriching the contents worked on and offering an additional space for participatory reflection. To evaluate the students' perception, satisfaction questionnaires were applied with a Likert scale from 0 to 4, where 0 represented the worst evaluation ("very bad") and 4 the best ("very good"), collected through Google Forms. This instrument allowed the collection of structured ratings on three key dimensions:

1. The organisation and distribution of activities,
2. The quality of content and presentations,
3. The facilities where they took place.

In addition, three open-ended questions were included to capture personal and qualitative impressions of the attendees:

- The main feelings after participating in the project,
- The most salient positive elements,
- And proposals for improvement for future activities.

The quantitative evaluations exceeded in all cases the success threshold of 3 points established in the project design. In the qualitative responses, the clarity of the presentation, the practical usefulness of the topics addressed, the professionalism of the speakers and the overall good organisation were particularly highlighted. The participatory approach of the dialogue spaces was also positively valued, although some people pointed out as an aspect to be improved the need to include more applied examples or to increase the degree of direct interaction during the sessions.

In the fifth structured dialogue, the satisfaction questionnaire was not finally applied, although it was already prepared and ready to be collected through Google Forms. The activity counted with the participation of the guest speaker Elena Valenciano, who travelled from the Valencian Community at a particularly complex time due to the DANA weather episode in Spain, which made it necessary to adjust the times due to urgent personal commitments. In addition, the session was considerably extended due to the high level of interest among the attendees, and it was considered a priority to preserve the final conversation space, in which the students were able to approach the guest in a more informal way and dialogue with her. This decision fully responded to the spirit of the project, which focuses on the creation of participatory and horizontal spaces, where direct contact and closeness with the guests are a fundamental part of learning. Although no quantitative data were collected, qualitative observations during the closing indicated a very positive assessment by the students.

The questionnaire designed to evaluate the sixth and last structured dialogue had a special value within the set of project activities. Unlike other more general forms, this instrument was specifically designed to capture the students' perception of a session focused on youth participation, shared leadership and the active representation of young people as experts. Given that the theme of the meeting revolved around the Youth Goals themselves, and that the dialogue was led by student partners in the project, different items were incorporated than usual

Specifically, this included a first part focused on logistical and organisational aspects (such as the suitability of the venue and timetable, the dynamics of the session or the sufficiency of the information), a second section on the content and the experience lived - evaluating, among others, the usefulness of the final manifesto, the youth protagonism in the conduct of the meeting, the richness of the interdisciplinary approach, and the importance of statistics in public policies -, and a third part of open questions that allowed participants to freely express what they liked most, what they would change in public policies, and what they would change in the future, the richness of the interdisciplinary approach, and the importance of statistics in public policies -, and a third part of open questions that allowed participants to freely express what they liked the most, what they would change in youth policies and what proposals for the future they would like to develop within the YGRC. This structure made it possible to collect data not only on the quality of the event, but also on the personal impact, the level of identification with the topics discussed and concrete proposals for improving youth participation in decision-making. Overall, this questionnaire provided a rich and nuanced vision, fully aligned with the methodological and pedagogical approach of the project.

One of the most significant elements of the sixth structured dialogue was the elaboration of the youth manifesto, a collective document that gathers ideas, demands and proposals around the Youth Goals from the direct voice of the young people themselves. The manifesto started from a base constructed by the group of student collaborators of the project, who, after their years of collaboration, work and learning around this theme, proposed the initial axes of the document. During the final dialogue, the manifesto was enriched and completed in a participatory manner by the participants, using the digital tool Padlet, which also allowed them to familiarise themselves with a new collaborative resource in educational contexts. This experience not only encouraged joint reflection and commitment to the objectives worked on, but also offered a practical example of collective **knowledge** construction, in line with the values of inclusion, horizontality and youth empowerment promoted by the *Youth Goals Research Centre* project.

Overall, the data obtained - although diverse in format and degree of systematisation - reflect a high level of satisfaction with the structured dialogues, which have been perceived as valuable spaces for reflection, expression and youth involvement. These meetings have strengthened the link between youth, politics and evidence, and have consolidated a pedagogical model where youth protagonism, respect for diversity and active participation are central. It is recommended to maintain this methodological flexibility in future editions, reinforcing the use of light but meaningful tools to capture the voice of the participants.

A more detailed analysis of the results obtained in the sixth structured dialogue is presented below, given its particular relevance within the project. This activity, led entirely by young participants from the *Youth Goals Research Centre*, not only incorporated a specific and thematically adapted evaluation questionnaire, but also generated tangible products such as the collective manifesto of young voices. The analysis of the responses collected, both quantitative and qualitative, allows us to offer a deeper insight into the formative impact, the perceptions of the students and the proposals that emerged in this space.

First, students participating in the structured dialogue - young university students belonging to the project's target social profile - were asked to select the *Youth Goal* with which they most identified. The most mentioned option was Goal 6: Empowering rural youth, with 21.9% of responses, followed by a group of equally represented goals: Goal 1: Connecting the EU with young people, Goal 3: Inclusive societies, Goal 5: Mental health and well-being, and Goal 7: Quality employment for all, all with 12.5% of mentions. Other goals identified by the group were Gender equality, Information and constructive dialogue, and Quality learning, reflecting a diversity of concerns and priorities among the young participants, closely linked to their social, educational and territorial realities. The objective with the lowest level of identification was Youth Goal 11: European programmes and youth organisations, selected by only 3.1% of the respondents.

Figure 1 Youth Goal most representative of participants

Content and experience

In relation to the specific contents of the meeting, the introduction to the *Youth Goals Research Centre* was rated positively by 93.8% of the participants (levels 4 and 5 on the scale), which indicates that the initial session managed to clearly convey the purpose of the project.

Likewise, the presence of young people from different disciplines was widely recognised as an enriching factor: 90.7% considered that this diversity added value to the conversation, favouring a broader, cross-cutting and representative view of the topics discussed.

The dialogue space was also well received: 81.2% said it allowed for reflection on issues relevant to young people, confirming that the format met its objective of encouraging critical thinking and the expression of real concerns in a horizontal environment.

One of the most significant findings was the high level of agreement on the importance of statistics and data analysis in the evaluation and implementation of public policies: 84.gave it the highest score, thus reinforcing the project's approach of promoting informed and evidence-based youth participation.

Figure 2 Assessment of the thematic content and interdisciplinary approach of the Dialogue

Finally, the final manifesto, conceived as a tool for collecting concrete proposals, was rated as useful by 81.3% of the students (Figure 3). This result supports the incorporation of mechanisms that not only encourage reflection, but also channel participation into tangible products, promoting collective commitment and facilitating the translation of ideas into concrete actions.

Figure 3 Assessment of the usefulness of the young voices manifesto developed

Youth leadership and perception of the format

A five-star visual scale was used to assess the public's perception of the fact that the session was led by young people. The average score was 4.59 out of 5, with 83% of responses at the maximum score. This result reflects a very high appreciation of the intergenerational and horizontal approach of the dialogue, underlining the positive impact for the students of seeing people of their own age group leading and moderating formative and participatory spaces.

In addition to the quantitative result, this decision was also very well received in the open-ended responses. Most of the comments highlighted that the youth leadership generated a greater emotional closeness, a more comfortable and participatory atmosphere, and a greater identification with the shared experiences. Terms such as *inspiring*, *useful*, *different*, *motivating* or *satisfying* were frequently repeated. Some participants mentioned that seeing their own peers leading the session made them feel represented and proud, and that this structure breaks with the traditional format of university activities, favouring a more active involvement.

There were also important nuances: one person expressed not feeling completely represented by the profiles of those leading the session, which underlines the need to continue promoting diversity within these spaces, both in terms of background and life trajectories. Overall, this assessment confirms that the direct participation of young people as protagonists of the dialogue was one of the main successes of the meeting.

Logistics and organisation

Figure 4 shows the students' perception of various logistical and organisational aspects of the activity. In all the items evaluated - dynamics of the session, sufficiency of information, total duration of the meeting and appropriateness of the venue and timetable - there is a clear trend towards higher ratings. In all cases, more than 80 % of the students expressed agreement or strong agreement, with the organisation of the dynamics and the appropriateness of the duration standing out in particular, both with a majority percentage in the "Strongly agree" option. These results reflect a good general planning and a high satisfaction with the development of the event.

Some aspects are highlighted in more detail below:

- With regard to the assessment of the venue and timetable, 84.4% of the participants (levels 4 and 5) considered them to be adequate, with 56.3% giving them the highest score.
- Regarding the information received during the session, 84. also considered it sufficient (levels 4 and 5), although 15.6% expressed that it was only partially sufficient, which suggests that in future editions a greater depth or broadening of contents could be envisaged, especially for participants with a more advanced level of involvement or prior knowledge.
- The duration of the meeting was rated as appropriate by 90.6 % of the learners, with 62.5 % scoring the highest mark, indicating that the time was perceived as well adjusted to the dynamics and objectives of the session.
- The overall organisation of the session received a particularly positive rating, with 93.8% of high scores (levels 4 and 5), highlighting the clarity in the conduct of the meeting and the orderly structure of the interventions.

One of the most relevant results was the level of comfort in participating, where 93.7% of the participants stated that they felt comfortable or very comfortable expressing their ideas. This figure reflects the creation of a safe, open and respectful environment, a fundamental element for the success of a space for youth participation such as this one. The sense of trust generated encouraged young voices to express themselves freely, fulfilling one of the central objectives of the structured dialogue format.

Figure 4 Assessment of the organisational aspects of the Structured Dialogue

Youth voices: open perspectives, proposals, criticisms and evaluation of experience

In addition to the structured assessment of the organisational, methodological and content aspects, the questionnaire included a series of open questions that offered a rich and nuanced view of the opinions, interests and proposals of the participating students. Through the qualitative analysis of these responses, it was possible to identify recurring thematic lines that not only add value to the diagnosis of the experience, but also allow us to project lessons and recommendations for future youth participation initiatives. The following are the main emerging axes around three key questions: how to encourage greater listening to young people's voices in decision-making, what aspects would change in current youth policies, and what was the most valued aspect of the experience lived in the framework of the structured dialogue.

The open-ended responses show a clear willingness to act on the part of young people, along with a critical understanding of the current limitations of their participation.

How do you think we can make the voice of young people more heard in decision-making?

The responses obtained show a clear willingness to act on the part of young people, accompanied by a critical view of the current barriers to their participation. Five key lines of action were identified:

1. Encourage political participation and direct action.
Many responses insist on the need to create real opportunities for political involvement, both from institutions and from civil society. Some more symbolic or extreme expressions reflect, above all, accumulated generational frustration.
2. Structured spaces for intergenerational dialogue.
The existence of forums such as this one is particularly valued, as well as the creation of stable dialogue roundtables in spaces such as the university. There is also a call for young people to be part of the real decision-making bodies, not only in parallel or symbolic structures.
3. Political education and awareness-raising.
There is a strong need for specific training in active citizenship, enabling young people to participate in a critical and informed way, developing an awareness of their social role.
4. Dissemination and visibility of opportunities.
There is a call for better institutional and community communication of the existing spaces and tools for participation, accompanied by motivational campaigns aimed at the youth environment.
5. Symbolic value and real representativeness.
Respondents also call for a fairer recognition of youth as political actors. The superficial use of quotas or "youth" spaces is questioned, calling for effective and diverse representation.

What would you like to change in policies affecting youth?

The proposals collected show a critical but constructive attitude, with a strong desire to transform both policy design and implementation. Five strands stand out:

1. Increased effectiveness and real application.
It is demanded that youth policies stop being only speeches or electoral promises, and become visible actions with concrete results and reasonable timeframes.
2. Connection to real needs.
It is stressed that policies must respond to everyday problems such as employment, education, mental health or participation, by genuinely listening to the concerns of young people.

3. Youth inclusion and representation.
Active participation in policy-making is seen as key: it is not enough to be recipients, young people want to be active agents and co-producers of the decisions that affect them.
4. Accessibility and a transformative approach.
It points to the need for a clearer, more comprehensible and transformative approach, avoiding paternalistic or simplistic views of what it is to be young.
5. Resources and institutional commitment.
It calls for greater public investment and cross-cutting commitment, with the involvement not only of the state, but also of local, business and universities in the promotion of these policies.

What I liked most about the activity

Through the qualitative analysis of the open-ended questions, several elements were identified as being particularly valued by the participating students:

1. The final manifesto and the use of Padlet.
The manifesto was widely recognised as a useful and motivating tool for expressing ideas. The use of Padlet was valued for its visual, dynamic and collaborative nature, which allowed for agile and creative participation.
2. Youth protagonism in the running of the meeting.
It was repeatedly emphasised that it was young people who led the session, as this generated greater identification, closeness and motivation to participate.
3. Spaces for the expression of ideas.
Many comments appreciated having had the real opportunity to intervene, to build collective ideas and to feel listened to in a respectful environment.
4. Specific interventions.
Some specific presentations were mentioned positively, such as those of students from the area of Political Science or the participation of a guest speaker.
5. The statistical and thematic approach.
The incorporation of statistical and technical analysis as part of the content was also appreciated, valuing its direct application to the field of youth public policies.

Overall, the responses collected reflect a youth that is committed, critical and capable of making proposals, that values spaces where they can express themselves, be heard and build collectively. The ideas that emerged from this structured dialogue not only provide valuable inputs for the project, but also for the design of more inclusive, realistic public policies that are connected to young voices. Above all, they made us proud of the talent, maturity and transformative energy of the young people who took part in the meeting.

CONCLUSIONS

The structured dialogues developed in the framework of the Youth Goals Research Centre project have proven to be significant spaces for meeting, learning and collective construction between youth, science and politics. Through a participatory and flexible approach, these meetings have facilitated the direct expression of the concerns, proposals and demands of young people, and in general of the attendees (workers of private entities, government entities, NGOs, academic and research staff, ...), offering an innovative framework for thinking about public policies from the evidence and the voice of citizens.

The diversity of formats, profiles and methodologies has allowed each session to be adapted to its context, always maintaining the focus on youth protagonism, the horizontality of the exchange and the connection with the real challenges faced by European youth. Beyond individual learning, the results obtained -qualitative and quantitative- show the value of these spaces as mechanisms for active listening, collective diagnosis and promotion of transformative proposals.

The participants especially valued the possibility of sharing time and real space with such high-level speakers, highlighting the closeness, listening and mutual respect as differential elements that deeply enriched the training experience.

The final dialogue, led by young people, symbolised in a particularly powerful way the spirit of the project: youth informed, empowered and able to influence decision-making. The joint elaboration of the manifesto and the high level of satisfaction with the experience reinforce this vision.

It is therefore concluded that the structured dialogues have fulfilled a dual function: pedagogical, by fostering critical thinking and data literacy, and political, by promoting real and meaningful participation of young people in building a more inclusive, just and evidence-based society.

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